

Report for CityMove Stakeholder Survey
CityMove Survey Overview

Response Statistics

	Count	%
Complete	93	98.9
Partial	1	1.1
Disqualified	0	0
Totals	94	

1. CONSENT

Value	Percent	Count
Yes, CityMove may identify me by name or function in any reports or publications using information obtained from me.	70,2%	66
No, CityMove may NOT identify me by name or function in any reports or publications using information obtained from me.	29,7%	28
	Totals	94

2. Please tell us which city you are actively working in (2024 onwards)

Value	Percent	Count
Kampala	29,8%	28
Antwerp	24,5%	23
Ljubljana	19,1%	18
Bogota	14,9%	14
Lima	5,3%	5
Rotterdam	4,3%	4
Other - (please specify)	2,1%	2
	Totals	94

3. Within your country which level do you usually work at?(tick all that apply)

Value	Percent	Responses
City / local level	73.6%	67
National Level	38.5%	35
Community / Neighbourhood Level	25.3%	23
Other - (please specify) (click to view)	8.8%	8

By city:

4. Select which best describes your organisation

By city:

5. What is your primary field of work within the promotion of health through physical activity?

Value	Percent	Responses
Walking and cycling promotion	39.4%	37
Programme development and implementation	33.0%	31
Research, data collection and evaluation	33.0%	31
Policy development	33.0%	31
Public space improvement / Infrastructure	28.7%	27
Education / Capacity building	25.5%	24
Communications / Advocacy	23.4%	22
Urban Planning	22.3%	21
<u>Other - (please specify) (click to view)</u>	14.9%	14
Financing mechanisms	5.3%	5
Governance models	4.3%	4

6. To create active societies, in your opinion, how likely is it that by 2030 your city will..

	Unlikely		Likely		Don't know		Responses
	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count
Implement best practice communication campaigns	7	7.5%	75	80.6%	11	11.8%	93
Promote the co-benefits of physical activity	3	3.2%	87	93.5%	3	3.2%	93
Provide regular mass participation events	8	8.7%	76	82.6%	8	8.7%	92
Build workforce capacity across government sectors	33	35.9%	36	39.1%	23	25.0%	92

7. To create active environments, in your opinion, how likely is it that by 2030 your city will..

	Unlikely		Likely		Don't know		Responses
	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count
Integrate transport and urban planning policies	19	20.9%	58	63.7%	14	15.4%	91
Improve the walking infrastructure conditions	8	8.6%	75	80.6%	10	10.8%	93
Improve the cycling infrastructure conditions	11	11.8%	75	80.6%	7	7.5%	93
Improve road safety and personal safety	18	19.6%	63	68.5%	11	12.0%	92
Strengthen the access to public open spaces	15	16.1%	63	67.7%	15	16.1%	93
Strengthen policies for active facilities and universal access	19	20.9%	55	60.4%	17	18.7%	91

8. To create active people, in your opinion, how likely is it that by 2030 your city will...

	Unlikely		Likely		Don't know		Responses
	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count
Enhance physical education and school based programs	22	23.9%	45	48.9%	25	27.2%	92
Incorporate physical activity into health and social services	18	19.6%	58	63.0%	16	17.4%	92
Provide public physical activity programmes across multiple environments	11	12.1%	63	69.2%	17	18.7%	91
Improve provision of physical activity programmes for older adults	18	20.0%	51	56.7%	21	23.3%	90
Prioritise physical activity programmes for the least active groups	27	30.0%	40	44.4%	23	25.6%	90
Support community-led initiatives	13	14.4%	61	67.8%	16	17.8%	90

9. To create active systems, in your opinion, how likely is it that by 2030 your city will...

	Unlikely		Likely		Don't know		Responses
	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count
Strengthen policy, leadership and governance systems	25	26.9%	51	54.8%	17	18.3%	93
Improve and integrate data systems for monitoring	20	21.7%	53	57.6%	19	20.7%	92
Build research and evaluation capacity	20	21.7%	48	52.2%	24	26.1%	92
Expand advocacy efforts	18	19.6%	44	47.8%	30	32.6%	92

Develop innovative finance mechanisms	26	28.0%	31	33.3%	36	38.7%	93
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10. Human rights approach: In your opinion, do the physical activity actions in your city promote human rights and involve communities in the development of solutions that benefit health?

Value	Percent	Count
Yes	55.4%	51
No	28.3%	26
Don't know	16.3%	15
Totals		92

11. Equity across the life course: In your opinion, do the physical activity policies consider the different groups and needs (by gender, disability, socioeconomic status, and geography) to address disparities in physical activity participation?

Value	Percent	Count
Yes	54.4%	49
No	28.9%	26
Don't know	16.7%	15
	Totals	90

12. Evidence based practice: In your opinion, are the physical activity policies in your city based on scientific evidence and practice evidence?

Value	Percent	Count
Yes	49.4%	44
Don't know	29.2%	26
No	21.3%	19
	Totals	89

13. Proportional universality: In your opinion, is the resource allocation proportional to the physical activity actions needed to engage the least active and those who face the greatest barriers to increasing participation?

Value	Percent	Count
No	61.1%	55
Don't know	23.3%	21
Yes	15.6%	14
Totals		90

14. Policy coherence and health in all policies: In your opinion, are physical activity actions across policies and between partners to achieve sustained change and impact?

Value	Percent	Count
Yes	60.0%	54
No	20.0%	18
Don't know	20.0%	18
	Totals	90

15. Engagement and empowerment of policy makers, people, families and communities: In your opinion, are people and communities empowered and actively engaged in the development of policies and interventions that affect them?

Value	Percent	Count
No	60.4%	55
Yes	24.2%	22
Don't know	15.4%	14
	Totals	91

16. Multi-sectoral partnerships. In your opinion, is there collaboration across and between stakeholders guided by a shared vision?

Value	Percent	Count
Yes	47.2%	42
No	29.2%	26
Don't know	23.6%	21
	Totals	89

17. The CityMove project is offering training to support the development of capacity for better physical activity outcomes. Please select all modules of interest:

TRAINING PRIORITIES	Yes	%	No	%	TOTAL
Equity and universal access	63	84%	12	16%	75
Research and evidencebased practice	70	85,4%	12	14,6%	82
Policy coherence and governance	66	77,6%	19	22,4%	85
Community engagement and empowerment	67	84,8%	12	15,2%	79
Multi-Sectorial Partnership	54	69,2%	24	30,8%	78
Reporting, monitoring frameworks and indicators	63	79,7%	16	20,3%	79
Resource mobilisation	64	79,0%	17	21%	81

City Comparison

5. Within your country which level do you usually work at? (tick all that apply)

8. To create active societies, in your opinion, how likely is it that by 2030 your city will...

	Unlikely	Likely	Don't know	Responses
	Row %	Row %	Row %	Count
Implement best practice communication campaigns				
Antwerp	9.1%	81.8%	9.1%	22
Ljubljana	9.1%	72.7%	18.2%	11
Rotterdam	%	%	100.0%	2
Kampala	14.3%	78.6%	7.1%	14
Bogota	%	100.0%	%	11
Lima	%	80.0%	20.0%	5
Promote the co-benefits of physical activity				
Antwerp	%	95.5%	4.5%	22
Ljubljana	%	100.0%	%	11
Rotterdam	%	100.0%	%	2
Kampala	14.3%	85.7%	%	14
Bogota	%	100.0%	%	11

Lima	%	100.0%	%	4
Provide regular mass participation events				
Antwerp	4.5%	86.4%	9.1%	22
Ljubljana	%	100.0%	%	11
Rotterdam	%	100.0%	%	2
Kampala	28.6%	71.4%	%	14
Bogota	%	63.6%	36.4%	11
Lima	%	100.0%	%	4
Build workforce capacity across government sectors				
Antwerp	54.5%	18.2%	27.3%	22
Ljubljana	63.6%	9.1%	27.3%	11
Rotterdam	100.0%	%	%	2
Kampala	35.7%	42.9%	21.4%	14
Bogota	18.2%	45.5%	36.4%	11
Lima	%	75.0%	25.0%	4

12. Human rights approach
In your opinion, do the physical activity actions in your city promote human rights and involve communities in the development of solutions that benefit health?

19. The CityMove project is offering training to support the development of capacity for better physical activity outcomes. Please select all modules of interest:

	Yes, please		No, thanks		Responses
	Count	Row %	Count	Row %	Count
Equity and universal access					
Antwerp	15	75.0%	5	25.0%	20
Ljubljana	3	33.3%	6	66.7%	9
Rotterdam	1	50.0%	1	50.0%	2

Kampala	12	85.7%	2	14.3%	14
Bogota	7	87.5%	1	12.5%	8
Lima	3	100.0%	0	%	3
Research and evidence-based practice					
Antwerp	16	76.2%	5	23.8%	21
Ljubljana	6	60.0%	4	40.0%	10
Rotterdam	1	50.0%	1	50.0%	2
Kampala	13	92.9%	1	7.1%	14
Bogota	9	100.0%	0	%	9
Lima	4	100.0%	0	%	4
Policy coherence and governance					
Antwerp	15	71.4%	6	28.6%	21
Ljubljana	4	50.0%	4	50.0%	8
Rotterdam	0	%	1	100.0%	1
Kampala	13	92.9%	1	7.1%	14
Bogota	7	63.6%	4	36.4%	11
Lima	4	100.0%	0	%	4
Community engagement and empowerment					
Antwerp	16	76.2%	5	23.8%	21
Ljubljana	5	62.5%	3	37.5%	8
Rotterdam	2	100.0%	0	%	2
Kampala	11	91.7%	1	8.3%	12
Bogota	8	88.9%	1	11.1%	9
Lima	3	100.0%	0	%	3
Multi-Sectorial Partnership					
Antwerp	8	44.4%	10	55.6%	18
Ljubljana	3	37.5%	5	62.5%	8
Rotterdam	0	%	2	100.0%	2
Kampala	13	100.0%	0	%	13
Bogota	8	80.0%	2	20.0%	10
Lima	3	100.0%	0	%	3
Reporting, monitoring frameworks and indicators					
Antwerp	13	65.0%	7	35.0%	20
Ljubljana	4	50.0%	4	50.0%	8
Rotterdam	1	50.0%	1	50.0%	2

Kampala	13	92.9%	1	7.1%	14
Bogota	9	100.0%	0	%	9
Lima	3	100.0%	0	%	3
Resource mobilization					
Antwerp	13	65.0%	7	35.0%	20
Ljubljana	4	44.4%	5	55.6%	9
Rotterdam	2	100.0%	0	%	2
Kampala	12	92.3%	1	7.7%	13
Bogota	7	77.8%	2	22.2%	9
Lima	3	100.0%	0	%	3

Other suggestions:

- Advocacy for inclusive infrastructure (Kampala)
- Community trust building (Kampala)
- Green Urban designs (Kampala)
- Inclusive urban spaces: (Kampala)
- Innovative approaches to promote PA (Ljubljana)
- Policy advocacy and engagement (Kampala)
- Private and public (Bogota)
- Public awareness for Mindset change (Kampala)
- Sustainability and innovation of projects and programs (Bogota)
- Community participation (Kampala)

20. Anything else you would like to share with the CityMove team?

Antwerp

ResponseID	Response
16	Als vrouwenorganisatie die werkt aan empowerment van vrouwen (van alle leeftijden, nieuwkomers en inwoners van Antwerpen) willen wij graag betrokken worden bij dit initiatief.
18	volgende vraagstelling was me niet duidelijk: uw mening gevraagd over hoeveel van deze principes er zijn, of zouden kunnen zijn. vb; Vindt er volgens u sprake van samenwerking tussen en tussen belanghebbenden, geleid door een gedeelde visie? Moet er deze er moeten zijn volgens mijn mening? Zou deze er kunnen zijn...dat zijn verschillende vragen en je kan maar 1 antwoord geven.
30	Neen, bedankt
34	Volgens ons kunnen bedrijfsleiders en werkgevers (maw organisaties), meestal vanuit HR, hier ook een belangrijke rol in spelen om hun medewerkers letterlijk (en figuurlijk) in beweging te brengen om hun sedentaire gedrag tegen te gaan. Het sociale en collectieve aspect is hier ook van cruciaal belang (creëer connectie met elkaar).
49	indien Gezond Leven vermeld wordt (in publicaties), worden we graag op voorhand ingelicht.
50	/
51	Wat een moeilijke vragen, kunnen jullie die niet eenvoudiger neerschrijven? "Multisectorale partnerschappen. Vindt er volgens u sprake van samenwerking tussen en tussen

	belanghebbenden, geleid door een gedeelde visie? Mee eens zijn Het oneens zijn Niet toestemmen of tegenstemmen "
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Ljubljana

ResponseID	Response
8	Spoštovani, z veseljem bom sodelovala na vaših izobraževanjih ter delila svoje strokovne izkušnje in izkušnje kot prebivalka MOL. Lep pozdrav Andrea Backović Juričan
55	Z veseljem sodelujem v kolikor bi potrebovali kakšno strokovno raziskovalno pomoč ali pomoč iz vidika vključevanja skupnosti, saj sem tudi učiteljica joge.
65	srečno!

Kampala

ResponseID	Response
2	integrated solution based approaches
3	Training on Safety infrastructure and details/specifications of materials that can be used to implement active mobility routes and spaces
11	Nope. Looking forward to safer environments for mobility
21	The world is increasing becoming uncertain, there is need for collaboration across board, constant learning, and community needs assessment as we perse stability, prosperity and inclusivity, while dealing with convectional challenges (environment, social, economic, and political challenges)
26	The promotion of active mobility will need a multi pronged approach based on our local culture and settings. We know about 50% of travellers to Kampala are pedestrians while 15-20% are cyclists but these have constantly been ignored in policy implementation. We need advocacy for policy where infrastructural planners will plan roads starting out to in as opposed to the current practice where as long motorized transport is catered for..all the others can fit in the remaining space. We also need to integrate PDPs to ensure continuity of projects and also advocated for urban planning to be prioritized by GoU bse its the foundation of all. The NMT corridor for example abruptly stops at ABSA Bank putting the same pedestrian it was protecting at risk. It has also been abused severally bse Urban planning was not given priority from the start and ofcourse currently enforcement is weak. We simple need to go back to basics and do the right thing bse a building without a foundation cannot stand.
27	I appreciate the idea and hope the project will come to fruition and yield excellent results for the good health of all Ugandans
43	Cycling lanes in restricted spaces
44	Note: Strategic integration and advocacy is a key component that contribute to sustainability of the Physical Activity Outcomes.
82	Communities involvement at the grassroots would be another option.
83	City move should come out, we need to hear it out. Wether on social media and the like. Its silent yet its a great program.
87	Traffic control measures say BRT, LRT
88	Together we can change our cities

90	All entities including media should be actively brought on board. Follow ups are important to ensure far reaching impact
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Bogota

ResponseID	Response
37	En mi ciudad hemos avanzado con espacio para la actividad física, es importante seguir por esta ruta
46	La implementación del proyecto CityMove tiene gran relevancia para la ciudad con el fin de tener elementos para evaluar el impacto de intervenciones innovadoras en la práctica de la actividad física para prevención de condiciones crónicas no transmisibles.
54	- La implementación de la IA en el proyecto y su aplicación práctica por parte de la ciudadanía y las entidades estatales. - Su complementariedad con la biodiversidad urbana
56	La Ciclovía de Bogotá, es un programa que frecuentemente adapta sus dinámicas operativas y administrativas, de acuerdo a los cambios que presente la ciudad y sus habitantes. De allí, que las acciones de prospectiva que se han desarrollado y que se siguen gestando, buscan anticipar acciones en beneficios de la comunidad que participa de forma directa e indirecta del programa.
57	Formación en el campo del deporte para integrarlos como actividad física
67	Agradecimiento por la tarea que están realizando y atenta a participar en futuros encuentros.
77	Es una estrategia de gran relevancia que permite a los diferentes actores institucionales aunar y fortalecer esfuerzos para la promoción de actividad física y prevención de CCN